

SYSTEM CONNECTIONS IN THE SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF KITCHEN VOCABULARY

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ABSTRACT

The article defined the title of "System connections in the semantic structure of kitchen vocabulary" aims to compare and contrast the lexical units used in the English and Uzbek languages when referring to household items, objects and activities. The article starts with a brief introduction to the importance of studying lexical units and their role in language acquisition, communication, and culture. The lexical units are categorized into semantic fields such as furniture, kitchenware, cleaning tools, etc. For each semantic field, the article presents a list of lexical units in both languages and analyzes their similarities and differences in terms of form, meaning, and usage.

The scientific expediency of the work is determined by the integrative nature of the vocabulary under consideration, combining an onomasiological basis and a continuous tendency to generalize new realities, including at the turn of the 20th - 21st centuries. Kitchen and household vocabulary has repeatedly become the object of study in various areas. Separate groups of this vocabulary were considered in the works of domestic linguists - V.N. Prokhorova - composition, semantics and lexical-thematic grouping of kitchen and everyday vocabulary in the texts of monuments of the 15th century; E.N. Bolonina - names of drinks, food products of animal and dairy origin, food in Russian business writing of the 15th-16th centuries, V.I. Nevoit (1986) - names of food and pitaya products in the Old Russian language; A.I. Leonova (2003) - linguocultural specificity of "culinary names" in Russian, English and French.

In line with linguistic and cultural developments, the concept of "food" is being actively studied. So, E.V. Filippova (2004) studied the distribution ("semantic isotopy") of descriptions of feasts and tea drinking from the point of view of the social functions of food using the material of short prose of the 60-80s. XX century According to E.V. Filippova (2004), on the basis of modern linguistic concepts, it is very fruitful to study the various connections between semantic specificity and social, cultural and historical factors precisely in this system of highly specialized vocabulary. Kitchen and everyday vocabulary, as a polysystem, was not considered in the complex of its semantic and linguocultural characteristics that form the

national-cultural semiotic paradigm. All of the above determines the relevance of the study. The subject of the study is the lexical-semantic and linguistic-cultural features of the kitchen and everyday vocabulary of the Russian language in its evolution.

Single-word and compound nominations included in the specified polysystem, extracted through continuous and representative samples from explanatory, word-formation, cultural, phraseological, etymological dictionaries and text sources (about 2 thousand units of description in total), considered both out of context and in discourse. The purpose of the study is to consider the lexical systematicity, linguocultural features and dynamics of kitchen and everyday vocabulary in the English language.

The set goal defines the following main tasks:

- 1) systematize and generalize modern linguistic approaches to the study of vocabulary as a system;
- 2) determine the composition of English kitchen and household vocabulary and carry out its thematic classification;
- 3) describe the structural and semantic properties of paradigmatic (synonymous and hyper-hyponymic) relations of the analyzed units;
- 4) consider the historical and social conditionality of the development of kitchen and everyday vocabulary, which is revealed in the semantic characteristics of the names of different thematic subgroups (food, cutlery, etc.), in the semantic and functional dynamics of the polysystem;
- 5) identify linguistic and cultural features in the categories of Russian kitchen and household vocabulary.

The methodological basis of the study is a systematic and analytical presentation of the object of philological research (works of domestic and foreign linguists: G.A. Abramova (2003), Yu.D. Apresyan (1995), M.A. Borodina (1979), V.V. Vinogradov (1977), A. Vezhbitskaya (1999), V. G. Gaka (1978, 1979), Y. N. Karaulova (1980), V. G. Kostomarova (1994), L. P. Krysinina (2002), S. O. I. Ozhegov (1974), V. N. Prokhorova (1994), A. A. Reformatsky (1987), Y. S. Stepanov (1977), O. N. Trubachev (2003), A. A. Ufimtseva (1968, 1977), L.V. Shcherby (1974), etc.).

The scientific novelty of the work is related to the nature of the problems being solved. For the first time, the ontological nature of the lexical layer associated with the concepts of "food/cuisine" has been revealed, linguistic and linguocultural trends have been identified, which make it possible to substantiate the unique dynamics of the polysystem under study, which connects archaic vocabulary layers with ultra-modern nominations. For the first time, the taxonomic parameters of the thematic group "cuisine" were systematically examined, and the dynamics of its units were traced.

The theoretical significance of the work lies in an in-depth conceptual presentation of kitchen and everyday vocabulary, including nominations for the sphere of everyday life of a modern person, and is determined in a historical-descriptive manner, taking into account the uniqueness of the object and the assigned tasks.

The practical feasibility of the research results is determined by their multifaceted didactic and lexicographic relevance. The linguistic and cultural value of the results is also natural, since kitchen and everyday vocabulary constitutes a certain informative value when

mastering English as a foreign language. The results obtained are applicable for a significant addition to explanatory, historical, and etymological dictionaries.

Kitchen and household nominations exhibit a specific systematicity in which anthropocentric dominants are determined. This subsystem of English vocabulary is revealed in the unity of stable and changeable aspects that determine the deeply specific mutual orientation of a person and fragments of the external world transformed by him.

Everyday vocabulary denoting drinks, food and dishes in the Old English language was a fairly extensive, unified and definitely organized system. In the analyzed lexical group, diachronically, the same thematic associations of words are observed, consisting of lexical-semantic groups in which components (words and phrases of a nominative nature) are interconnected by synonymous, generic relations, based on general and differentiating semantic features or by the similarity of the expressed meanings.

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